

Historical trains invaded by fluffy stuff. Mould issues in six historical train interiors: treatment and follow-up.

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After their extraordinary history, six magnificent train wagons lie in a workshop declared unusable by the fire department. The owner decides to hermetically seal the wagons against light and - capital mistake – heating as well.

This awakens incubated populations and they infest every nook and cranny of the interiors. The organisms play a double role: of aggressors and of saviours. Saviours because this prodigious infestation so alarms experts that a conservation project is ultimately launched. The wagon doors are thrown open and we - the Royal Institute for Cultural Heritage in Brussels (KIK-IRPA) – become the next witnesses to this unique heritage.

▪ *The interiors of two historical train wagons From left to right: 1901, 1901 and 1905*
© KIK-IRPA, Brussels

▪ *The interiors of four historical train wagons From left to right: 1939 – 1912 – 1939 – 1939*

Introduction

Six unique historical train interiors that belong to the cultural heritage of the National Railway Company of Belgium (SNCB) were affected by mould about five years ago. This mould problem arose due to a combination of poor storage conditions and rash decisions. Four of the six carriages are still in the workshop that was rejected as unusable by the fire department a few years ago. The personnel were transferred, meaning that surveillance was at risk: this was in fact why the carriages were totally sealed. The heating in the workshop was also switched off after some time and this gave rise to grave moisture problems: a veritable paradise for mould.

The SNCB's prestigious project "Train World" (Belgian national museum), where two of the six carriages were to be the showpiece at the end of September 2015, forced a reassessment, and the realisation of the need for decontamination and conservation quickly provided the required impetus.

The concerned department within the SNCB started looking for a solution. Should they "clean" the unique articles using their own personnel, or should they obtain advice from external specialists?

At the end of 2012, the SNCB took the plunge and commissioned the preventive conservation unit of the KIK-IRPA to carry out the job. Two years earlier, the SNCB had itself refurbished a wagon under an international loan-for-use arrangement. That they nevertheless contacted the KIK-IRPA to tackle this problem, demonstrates a new approach to handling their historical heritage.

An *in situ* visit quickly revealed the complexity of the problem and the approach to it. The storage location was poorly equipped.¹ Concrete decay, holes and leaks in the roof made the professional preservation of such train interiors impossible. The owners of the SNCB were aware of this, but shifting the trains was obviously not an option, considering the absence of good storage spaces within its own organisation. Shifting carriages that had not been in operation since 1976 would also be a very cumbersome and risky move. The explosion of mould growth had therefore to be stabilised *in situ* and had to be combated with a thorough-going approach.

Of course, a second problem was related to the complexity of this type of heritage: large objects (wagons) containing small, often difficult to access object parts (compartments), with a multitude of different types of materials (wood, marquetry, paintings, textiles, glass, ceramic materials, metal, linoleum, etc.). It would be impossible to find one single specialist who would have all the required knowledge of the materials involved in this contract. A comprehensive interdisciplinary team would now have to look for a solution in close collaboration with each other.

The report of our first site visit described our vision of the future approach, and presented a concrete plan of action. In view of the complexities involved, the SNCB requested us for a meeting with all the concerned managers to provide the required clarifications and explanations. During this key moment, KIK-IRPA made it clear that we should no (longer) approach the trains as a functional object, but as historical heritage. We were requested to coordinate the decontamination project. Before we could start on this contract, we emphatically underlined the crucial importance of care after the work had been executed. Something that is unjustly often overlooked. The large budgets that would have to be cleared for coordination and execution were of such magnitude that it would be irresponsible not to take these observations into account. Efforts toward ensuring better internal conservation and management in the future, *and* looking for a new storage location for the carriages was our precondition for further collaboration.

¹ Building class 3 – building-type: non-isolated more or less closed (steel)constructions – climate class C/D (ASHRAE 2007): Ankersmit B., *Klimaatwerk. Richtlijnen voor het museale binnenklimaat*, Amsterdam University Press 2009, p. 28 and 87.

With the start of the climate measurements in the depot and the wagons, we made our offer, based on work phases. We formulated a detailed procedural sequence comprising five major phases, distributed over nine months:

1. Stabilising the extent of the mould attack
2. A detailed preliminary study
3. (Mechanical) removal of the mould: conservation of the interiors by an external firm
4. Follow-up of the renovation of the exterior of the carriages
5. Risk analysis relating to the preservation and future storage location of the carriages

	Month 1	Month 2	Month 3	Month 4	Month 5	Month 6	Month 7	Month 8	Month 9
PHASE 1									
Dehumidification									
PHASE 2									
Taking samples of the mould									
Documentation prior to treatment - condition reports									
Cleaning tests									
PHASE 3									
Drafting specifications									
Award of the contract									
Kick-off meeting									
Tests: Cleaning Fixation									
Treatment proposal									
Training moment									
Treatment									
Evaluation and final delivery									
Reporting									
PHASE 4									
PHASE 5									
Site visits									
Collection of information									
Measurements									
Report recommendations									
Relocation of four carriages									

■ *Initial list of the planned work*

At the start of the project in April 2013, we had planned for a duration of nine months for the entire project. Its complexity - but more significantly the cumbersome structure within the SNCB, ensured that we suffered massive delays. Two years later, the project is still not fully complete. Two of the six carriages have been shifted to Train World and a solution is still to be found for the remaining four.

Phase 1: Stabilising the extent of the mould attack

The exponential mould growth had to be slowed down immediately. In January 2013, we commenced an initial emergency intervention in which air circulation was generated inside the trains. The compartment doors and the small swing windows were opened. Apart from ventilation, the relative humidity (RH) in the carriages also had to be brought down to below 60%, a critical limit for mould growth.²

² <http://www.conservationphysics.org/arnemag/arnemagn1.php>

- The first climate measurements were conducted in the depot between 12/04/2013 and 24/05/2013

The dehumidification with strict climate control was carried out in collaboration with the external firm BEPA (via public tender). In view of the long term exposure of the interior elements to a humid climate (around 72% RH), the dehumidification had to be carried out with all the necessary caution. The RH had to be reduced by a maximum of 3% per 24 hours, in order to allow the climate-sensitive materials and objects within the carriages the time to adjust.

The RH in the carriages was gradually reduced from 73.5% to 53% over a span of 30 days. 53% RH was taken as the setting point and the average value was selected since in all probability this would reduce the risk of mechanical damage to the most vulnerable textile materials, veneer, modern materials, etc... First, the dehumidifiers were adjusted to lower the RH value, by 3%, every four days. From 60% onwards, the RH fell by 1.5% every four days. After reaching the target value of 53% RH, it had to be maintained, and ventilation and a constant air flow became extremely important.

During the dehumidification, we also checked the mould activity by taking mould samples at various times. Although we always found positive mould activity, there was lower germination of the mould spores in each case. In the beginning, germination was found even after two days; after 10 months of dehumidification, germination was only found after every three to four days. The conclusion that may cautiously be drawn from this is that the dry atmosphere had its effect on the mould activity.³

³ Brokerhof, A. , Van Zanen, B. & den Teuling, A. 2007, *Fluffy Stuff: Integrated control of mould in archives*, Instituut Collectie Nederland, Amsterdam; Guild, S. & Macdonald, M. 2003, *Mould prevention and collection recovery: Guidelines for heritage collections*, in *Technical Bulletin 26*, Canadian Conservation Institute, p. 23.

Phase 2: A detailed preliminary study

General

The complicated and comprehensive project made an extensive preliminary investigation absolutely necessary. Many questions had to be answered before a real beginning could be made. How extensive was the damage? Was there only surface mould? What were the potential treatment methods that we should opt for? Who would be able to take up the contract, and to whom should it be assigned? A professional cleaning company or a conservator-restorer, a train technician, etc.? How must this cleaning contract be approached and executed? Should we partially approach the carriages as a functional object that should be dismantled and repainted, or as a work of art in which there would be minimum intervention, and reversibility would be a top priority? Were there still other (ancillary) problems that might arise due to the high relative humidity? What about having a better storage location and aftercare in the long-term?

We realised that the management, conservation and presentation of historic rolling stock was by no means an easy task, but we did not doubt the premise. The wagons were no longer functional objects but part of historical heritage, in which the authenticity of the material was central. This appraisal determined the approach to the task.

Air analysis and photographs

At the start of the preliminary study, the climate in the depot and in other carriages was continuously monitored and thereafter analysed and interpreted. The results of mould samples and air analyses were mapped. The air analysis made it clear that the mould growth had assumed great proportions. The concentration of mould spores in the air (number of viable units per cubic metre or UFV/m³) was far above normal values in some cases. Where 800 UFV/m³ is the standard, a value of 1,500 UFV/m³ was found in some compartments. Individual protection in the carriages was extremely important!⁴

The KIK-IRPA photographers photographed the interiors extensively. The mould growth was also documented in detail.

- *Mould growth in the sleeping compartments (mattresses)*

Working photos. © KIK-IRPA, Brussels

⁴ Disposable half face respirators with the finest filter quality (FFP3), nitrile hand gloves and cleanroom overalls with hood and Tyvec boot covers.

- Mould growth on a broom sheet
- Mould growth on the linoleum floor under a bed

Condition reports

We drew up detailed condition reports for each carriage and compartment. These reports stated the degree and the location of the mould attack in each case and ultimately provided a clear picture of the degree of contamination. With the information from the preliminary investigation, we then drew up a detailed treatment plan.

Conditiereport PERCEEL 1: Rijtuig A1

V. Compartiment n° A1.5

1. Algemeen

Datum observatie:	29 april 2013	Omgevingsfactoren	Bewolkt: 8°C - 66% RV	
		Temperatuur	10.3°C	Uur:
		Relatieve vochtigheid	61.7%	9u

2. Overzicht

3. Overzicht schimmel contaminatie

Omschrijving object / onderdeel	Materiaal	Contaminatiegraad	Beschrijving
Vloer	Vast tapijt + linoleum		Linoleum zit onder het tapijt
Wanden			
Noordwand	Hout		
	Metaal (onderdelen)		
	Textiel		
Oostwand	Hout		
	Metaal (onderdelen)		
	Textiel		
Zuidwand	Hout		
	Metaal (onderdelen)		
	Textiel		
Westwand	Hout		
	Metaal (onderdelen)		
	Textiel		
Plafond	Textiel		waterschade
	Hout		

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- Page from the condition report: the colours represent the degree of mould attack, with red representing the most severely affected areas, while orange represents the moderately affected areas

Cleaning tests

We conducted *in situ* tests of cleaning products and methods with a team of ten conservator-restorers, each specialising in their own disciplines (glass, textile, wood, metal, painting, modern and ceramic materials). These indicated how stubborn the mould was and how it could be removed.

Restorers with protective clothing at work during cleaning tests Working photos. © KIK-IRPA, Brussels

After one day of *in situ* work, we realised that the method of working was more complicated than had earlier been imagined: what about the direction in which work would be conducted within the trains, how should the extremely fragile materials, carpets and corroded metals be handled? How were movable objects such as mattresses, sheets and blankets to be treated? Consistently working according to a well-defined and fixed method appeared to us to be of crucial importance.

	Material	Method	Material	Solvent	Observations
1.1	Metal	Dry cleaning	Swab	/	Good result, the entire mould infestation and the starting layer was removed after cleaning; during the cleaning, the necessary pressure had to be applied to the material Labour-intensive
1.2		Dry cleaning + disinfection with ethanol	Swab	Ethanol	Good result; somewhat better than (1.1)
1.3		Wet cleaning with ethanol	Swab	Ethanol	Good result; several repetitions required to remove the residue; faster than (1.1) and (1.2)

Example of cleaning tests on metal, with photograph Working photos. © KIK-IRPA, Brussels

Detailed photographs: some examples of cleaning tests on metal, linoleum and wood/marquetry

Procedural strategy

Based on a procedural strategy, we therefore laid down certain requirements:

- For each material present, we required a conservator-restorer with the relevant specialisation
- We emphasised mechanical and dry cleaning for the removal of the general surface mould. We used wet cleaning and disinfection wherever possible and necessary.
- General wear and tear through use had to be respected.
- Only in case of material loss with heavily corroded or damaged objects was additional conservation permitted. Coffee stains, water damage, impact damage, etc. were not to be restored, removed or retouched.

In the preliminary study, we envisaged that a full team of conservator-restorers would have to work in every carriage. But five conservators simultaneously working in a small sleeping compartment of 3m², was found to be a physical impossibility. Interdisciplinary and cross material work was the only solution. Each team member was required to train his colleagues according to his specialisation. Each specialist remained liable for his material type throughout the term of the contract.

Follow-up

Neither the carriages nor the interiors could be dismantled. We therefore had no idea what lay behind the walls and under the floors. After removing the surface mould and after disinfection (for example, of metal, glass, ceramic materials, etc.), the carriages would never be fully mould free. Coordinating and following up the execution thoroughly seemed to be the only thing that the project coordinator could control. Apart from follow-up, the success of the handling of a mould infestation of this magnitude also depended on the precision and the goodwill of the conservator-restorer and his team. Will the restorer, after working for four months in difficult circumstances, maintain concentration and carefully vacuum clean one spot in various directions?

From preliminary study to tender specifications

In order to reduce the risk of unrecognised and inexperienced conservator-restorers, we employed strict contract award criteria when describing the public contract (issued by the SNCB). In the tender specifications partially drawn up by us, the contract award criterion of ‘quality of the execution proposal’ was set on par with the contract award criteria ‘price’. Companies that did not score well on the quality component were thereby excluded from further participation.

The entire contract was sub-divided into six different lots. Each carriage was treated as a separate lot. The small firms or associated conservator-restorers could also participate. We thought this to be important because we felt that communication with a small company would be easier for us and would take place on a less ‘commercial’ footing than would be the case with a large firm. Here as well, we had to revise our initial conception. Ultimately, this consideration was found insignificant and a large firm was awarded the contract.

Smoke generator treatment

In order to tackle the problem of our inability to totally clear the mould from the carriages, we looked for a method/agent with which we could disinfect the carriages in bulk. Through colleagues, we found out about using smoke generating canisters.⁵

Smoke generator treatment involves exposing moulds in a particular area to smoke containing the fungicide Imazalil or Enilconazole. The advantage of the smoke generator method is that large rooms of up to 50m³ can be treated at one go, without having to manipulate each object separately. Furthermore, smoke generating canisters are used in the animal world for the prevention of the *Aspergillus* infection, which is of the same mould species as the one found in the wagons.

All these advantages encouraged us to investigate whether smoke generating canisters could be used to make the train interiors mould free. A test phase was introduced around the following questions:

- Is a residue left behind after the test?
- Can the smoke kill mould even in difficult to reach places?
- Does the smoke generating canister cause any irreversible damage to the interior of the carriages?

- *Smoke generating canister in operation during a test in a compartment of a carriage*

The smoke generating canister was tested in a small and closed part of a carriage. (see fig.) Before lighting the wick, ARA kit (swab) samples of the mould were taken from various places in the test zone. After the smoke test, samples were taken again.

The visible precipitate that was left behind after the test was negligible. The mould sample showed that the smoke generating canister had been effective. The samples that had been positive before the test, showed negative results after the smoke generator treatment. Furthermore, no visible damage such as discoloration, shrinkage or expansion of timber, or heat spots was seen. Possibly, the precipitation was less visible due to the already existing layer of dust, dirt and mould.

The smoke generating canisters had so far been found to produce positive results. The mould completely inactive, thereby reducing the risk of re-infestation. Further, more thorough laboratory research into the composition and effect of the residue was planned as our next phase.⁶

Unfortunately, the 'Clinafarm Smoke' smoke generating canister was transferred from one pharmaceutical company to another in late 2012. As soon as the stocks of Clinafarm Smoke were

⁵ Smoke generating canisters are manufactured for veterinary applications, more particularly for use in pens to kill pathogenic mould. The composition can be found in the Clinafarm Smoke™ directions for use.

⁶ The same questions have to be raised for the use of smoke generating canisters in archives, sacristies, etc. For contaminated manuscripts for example, the risk of deposition can not be accepted.

exhausted, it could not be found anywhere. A change in the registration following the company takeover was the reason for this. As a result, we were unable to use smoke generating canisters anymore and its use for cultural heritage had to be placed “on hold”. We hope to resume this research during 2016, as soon as the change in the registration is completed.

Phase 3: (Mechanical) removal of the mould: conservation of the interiors by an external firm

The external firm - Helicon Conservation Support - specialising in preventive conservation and calamities was awarded the entire contract. The collaboration between this external (service) provider and the KIK-IRPA commenced on 1st October 2014. During the kick-off meeting, the terms of the contract were clearly defined: the team, the planning and the treatment were discussed and we established the delivery protocol in order to prevent misunderstandings.

Work could finally be resumed! The appointed conservator-restorers, who were from various disciplines, investigated the interiors *in situ*. They started testing their own cleaning tests. They proposed a treatment for each material that was in line with our cleaning tests. A transfer of materials knowledge between the various restorers and the ultimate group of executing contractors took place. The carriages were taken up by a permanent team of three highly enthusiastic conservator-restorers.

The same method was consistently used for the six carriages: from top to bottom (from the ceiling to the floor), compartment by compartment and together in the direction of the ventilation flow of the dehumidifiers. They started work wearing full protection, equipped with a museum vacuum cleaner with HEPA filter⁷, a small bristle brush and a micro-fibre cloth. They cleaned the same surface several times and in various directions. Modern materials such as linoleum, plastic, Bakelite and rubber were dry cleaned or cleaned with demineralised water. Hard materials such as metal, glass and ceramic materials were disinfected with alcohol. Difficult to reach places such as behind ventilation grilles and heating elements were disinfected using an alcohol mist.

The practical work in the carriages lasted six months, of which one month went into preparatory work and one carriage every two weeks to three weeks.

Unforeseen problems

The time between the preliminary investigation (April 2013) and the ultimate start of the work (October 2014) was 18 months. Other biological infestations developed as they had had the time to grow.

The few moths that we found in April 2013 had multiplied during the 18 months. They had been feasting on all the rich textiles, particularly the carpets. This deterioration was primarily to be found under the beds and in difficult to reach places, due to which this problem was difficult to detect. As a result of the insect damage, the top layer of the carpets was in a fragile state. (see next fig.)

⁷ HEPA stands for High Efficiency Particulate Air filter or High Efficiency Particulate Absorbing filter. It applies to every appliance that is capable of filtering at least 99,97% of the absorbed particles with a diameter greater than or equal to 0,3µm

- *Holes caused by moth damage*
- *Mould attack*

In view of the impairment and the risk of material loss, the carpets were not vacuumed immediately. It was decided to dismantle the carpets and to remove them from the carriages. A deep freeze treatment became necessary, as well as a more extensive conservation.

The entire team evaluated the moth problem, and decided not to use major pesticides such as gassing at this stage. With the winter period on the horizon, the activity and productivity of the moths was expected to reduce considerably. In addition, the cleaning of the interiors would possibly halve the moth population. A good and strict check-up of the interiors after the cleaning would turn out to be of crucial importance.

Gamma radiation or deep freeze drying?

The executing contractors requested us for permission to use all gamma radiation on all the movable objects that were vulnerable to mould and moths. We were reluctant because after treatment, the objects would be returned to a non-irradiated area and could have adverse effects such as fibre attenuation (and accelerated aging) – something that could not be underestimated.⁸

In consultation with the executing contractor, we took a decision to use gamma radiation on some of the mattresses that remained unseen during the inspections. The mattresses were heavily contaminated on the outside (see fig. p.5), but we were unable to view the condition of the interior of the same. All mattresses were again to be packed in kraft paper and cloth, after treatment – according to the original. Protected from air, light and ventilation, they would also continue to remain unseen during a future inspection round. The risk of the re-emergence of the mould attack was very high. The fact that a deep freeze treatment cost almost as much as the gamma radiation treatment, was another significant reason. The fragile carpets on the other hand would have to be freeze dried.

Ventilation flow

All movable objects were removed from the carriages to the extent possible, and treated in the external restoration workshop of the executing contractor. The emptying of the carriages increased

⁸ Havermans, J., Hadeel, A.A. & De Bruin, G. 2005, *Gammastralen contra schimmels: Een gezonde oplossing voor bedreigd archief- en bibliotheekmateriaal*, in *CR: interdisciplinair vakblad voor conservering en restauratie*, p. 35-37.

the workability in the small train compartments. The ventilation flow of the dehumidifier that extended from one end of the carriage to the other, was thereby increased. (see the diagram below) When removing the mould, a good ventilation system was found to be extremely important. The executing contractor proposed the creation of three zones within the ventilation flow. A clean zone, a working zone and an infected zone. The clean zone was the zone that had been disinfected and cleaned, and entry into it after completion of work was prohibited. In the working zone, work was ongoing, and it was the location where all the required materials were stocked. The infected zone was the only access route to the working zone, and the untreated area was part of the workflow.

- *Entrance of the pulse tube of the dehumidifier to the carriage*
- *Diagram of the ventilation flow in a carriage: red represents the pulsed air, blue represents the discharged humid and contaminated air*

Phase 4: Follow-up of the renovation of the exterior of the trains

The two carriages that had to be sent to ‘Train World’, had to be worked on along the outer side. Dust, mould, grime and rust had to be removed. The SNCB decided to do this part of the work itself. The wagons delivered were to be disconnected from their dehumidifiers and shifted to a clean workshop without climate control in order to be worked on by the train mechanics. This caused us some anxiety.

After measurements, the workshop was found to have an ideal museum climate of 19°C and 50% RH. Through intensive communication with the mechanics and technicians, we worked again on mental reorientation. These historic carriages could not be treated in the same manner as present-day carriages, and aggressive cleaning agents were to be avoided. Thus for example, the textile exterior walls had to be cleaned with a vacuum cleaner with HEPA filter, and parts that were contaminated by mould had to be disinfected with ethanol. The roofs of the trains were repainted in their original colours.

Phase 5: Risk analysis relating to the preservation and future storage location of the carriages

Rolling heritage is not simply to be placed in some forgotten corner of a depot. These mastodons not only require space but also the maintenance they deserve as historical heritage.

The SNCB is struggling with lack of space and has no suitable depot available to it. In addition, it does not (as yet) have a professional team dedicated to taking care of historical carriages. Two of the ills that plague the heritage sector cropped up: absence of space and of money.

For this reason, we prepared an extensive advisory report in which we described the general collection requirements. We wanted to establish a clear view of what an ideal depot for such carriages should look like, and the criteria that the owner should apply when looking for a new storage location. We drew up a list of collection requirements, based on the most significant risks and hazards - the ten well-known agents of deterioration⁹. Everything was defined: at the level of the location, the building, the storage space, the carriages themselves, and the conservation policy. With the ten agents in the backs of our minds, we succeeded in defining general collection requirements, and action points for the long-term preservation of the carriages. Climate, ventilation, contamination, light, maintenance, inspection and safety were discussed.

In view of the mould problem, we were of the opinion that climate (but especially high RH) shall always be the greatest damage-causing factor. In case of poor climatological conditions, there is a great risk of new mould explosions. With the help of small tips and action points, such as isolating doors, connecting a heating system, moisture buffering, etc., it is possible to achieve some improvement in their existing depots.

The effect of light should also not be underestimated. Many materials in these carriages are extremely sensitive to light: wallpaper, textiles, carpets, upholstered furniture, natural rubber, veneer, pine, etc. A good museum lighting system tailor-made to the requirements must be ensured in Train World. An attempt was made to find our golden mean between maximum permissible luminance and aesthetic lighting requirements, in collaboration with the designers. We proposed the use of motion detectors in the museum, customised according to the lighting in the trains. Preconditions were laid down for access to the public and personnel and for the staging of events in the compartments.

We looked for suitable and budget-friendly solutions for shutter ventilation and contamination.

A maintenance and inspection plan was worked out. The better future preservation of the carriages primarily depends on the employees responsible for the same. Windows, doors, tables and floors cannot simply be cleaned with standard cleaning products. Through regular inspections, it will be possible to prevent calamities and limit damage to materials. Special attention should also be given to a future Integrated Pest Management plan.

In spite of our efforts to moderate the advisory report, it was still seen to be ambitious. But as a result of this report and the intensive collaboration of two and a half years (SNCB and KIK-IRPA), we were requested to provide aftercare through monitoring and inspections for at least one year.

The climate in Train World shall be evaluated and wherever necessary, adjusted. We shall prepare a clear sequence of operations for the maintenance and inspection rounds. The sensitisation will be increased through the request to arrange for training of some staff members of the SNCB and Train World so that they can gradually take over the task of aftercare.

⁹ *Preventive Conservation and Agents of Deterioration*, in *Canadian Conservation Institute*: <https://www.cci-icc.gc.ca/resources-ressources/agentsofdeterioration-agentsdedeterioration/index-eng.aspx>, accessed 06/08/2015.

Conclusion

Our collective victory: the two wagons in Train World are literally "on the right track." Their refurbished interiors and the exterior are now ready for viewing by the public. At present, minute attention is being paid to maintain a stable climate in the preserved interiors of the four other wagons. Despite the fact that four of the six unique carriages are still stored in the undersized and unsuitable depot, we are hopeful for the future. The SNCB has a strong will to take better care of its carriages from now on.

The heritage factor was decisive for the treatment methods, but also for the future carriage storage requirements. It also substantially affects the maintenance plan for the trains.

It is not just our SNCB colleagues of the "Historical Heritage" department who have to convince their cumbersome bureaucracy and governing boards of the need for a more object-oriented conservation. We as well have had to engage in a constant balancing act – in the opposite direction. As conservator-restorers, we were forced to consider a more global approach. The size of these Big Stuff objects and the complex approach to the mould catastrophe compelled us to find a middle path between both viewpoints. The project also evidenced many points of resemblance with the preservation of historic interiors in buildings as with the treatment of artefacts.

The inflexibility of a public enterprise of this size delayed matters for us on several occasions - which can often lead to risky situations for the conservation and management of six trains. Indeed, apart from concrete factors such as climate and maintenance that cause damage, the greatest risk factor consists in the bureaucracy and the difficulties experienced in convincing the general governing body. Nevertheless, three years of collaboration have clearly ensured greater sensitisation and trust – attitudes that require further nurturing. This is possibly also an ideal moment for the SNCB to develop official 'significance framework' for their mobile heritage, which – as part of a policy plan – could serve as a basis for long-term preservation, one that would be less subject to possible changes in managing bodies. It is not just these six historic carriages that deserve preservation. The other representative part of their historical mobile heritage must also be preserved for posterity. According to the research of the former Instituut Collectie Nederland (*Netherlands Institute for Cultural Heritage*, now RCE), such an indispensable significance framework would provide "a strong impetus for professionalization in the preservation of mobile heritage".¹⁰

¹⁰The ICN conducted a study on the value objectification of mobile heritage in 2005, in close collaboration with CIME/Stabien and the National Service for Archaeology, Cultural Landscape and Monuments. See Kok, A. 2009 *Erfgoed dat beweegt! Valuation of the Mobiele Collectie Nederland*, 2nd edition, Stokerkade cultuurhistorische uitgeverij, Amsterdam.

Detailed overview of the work done during the two and a half year project

1.	Development of mould problem within the six historic carriages
2.	SNCB starts searching for a solution: internal or external?
3.	SNCB contacts the preventive conservation department of the KIK-IRPA
4.	Climate measurements by the SNCB at the request of the KIK-IRPA, to provide an initial indication of the magnitude of the problem
5.	Visit by the KIK-IRPA to the depot and the 6 carriages
6.	First emergency intervention: making ventilation in the trains possible
7.	A preliminary report of the KIK-IRPA establishing the nature of the problem and proposing a plan of action for the short, medium and long term
8.	Meeting between the SNCB and the KIK-IRPA: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Discussion concerning the magnitude of the problem and the approach ▪ An agreement is arrived at between the SNCB and the KIK-IRPA, and the terms subject to which the KIK-IRPA would accept the project (aftercare and new storage location)
9.	Proposal: KIK-IRPA as project manager “Intervention in the mould problem.” A project sequence consisting of 5 phases with quotation, is proposed
10.	Climate measurements in the depot, and in the 6 carriages, over a period of 6 weeks
11.	Drawing up of specifications for the dehumidification of the interiors of the carriages: predetermined climatological target values + requirements: what must and what should not be done
12.	Comprehensive preliminary study: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Analysis of the air quality in the carriages ▪ ARA kit mould sampling from various materials in the carriages, at various times during the course of the project ▪ Drawing up detailed condition reports. The degree of contamination was specified with a colour code for each material in the various compartments. Even apparent damage was described. ▪ Work photos and professional photos of the train interiors prior to treatment ▪ Cleaning tests of the various materials (metal, wood, textile, glass, ceramics and modern materials)
13.	Commencement of the dehumidification process in the carriages: reduction from 73.5% RH to 53% RH in 30 days <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Phase 1: Fortnightly inspection by the KIK-IRPA, of how the materials had responded to the climate; climate control by external firm BEPA ▪ Phase 2: weekly to bi-monthly inspection by the KIK-IRPA, of how the materials had responded to the climate; climate control by external firm BEPA
14.	Discussions with the train technicians, the SNCB officers responsible for rolling stock, and with external specialists + international visits to museums and depots with similar collections
15.	Drawing up the technical requirements to be included in the specifications: detailed procedural sequence for treatment and sequence of the operations + planning
16.	Advising the SNCB concerning the eligibility conditions and contract award criteria for the public procurement contract
17.	Investigation for asbestos in three carriages by a specialist external firm
18.	Investigation into the use of smoke generating canisters and a smoke generator test in one compartment of a carriage
19.	Awarding of the contract for “Mechanical removal of mould and removal of dust from six train interiors” to one external firm
20.	Kick-off meeting with the SNCB, the KIK-IRPA and the external (service) provider: project definition, procedural sequence for planning and handling, drawing up the final delivery protocol + practical agreements
21.	Cleaning tests of the various materials by the external conservator-restorers Fixation and consolidation tests of the fragile materials and thickened paint layers Discussions concerning the metal corrosion
22.	Discussions concerning and definition of the treatment

23.	Knowledge transfer between the various conservator-restorers
24.	Fixing flaking paint layers
25.	Modification of the ventilation system and replacement of the HEPA filters of dehumidifiers
26.	Removable and loose objects (about 366) such as seats, mattresses, chairs, tables, cushions, textile, etc., removal from the carriages; photographing and drawing up a list of the same, packing and transporting them to an external restoration workshop
27.	Removal of the carpets from the carriages
28.	Mechanical removal of mould and removal of dust from 6 train interiors by the external team of 3 conservator-restorers
29.	Weekly to fortnightly inspection/site visits by the KIK-IRPA during the course of the work
30.	Bi-monthly inspection of the dehumidifiers and the climate in the carriages by the external firm
31.	Asbestos fibre measurements of the air in the carriages during the work, by a specialist external firm
32.	Provisional acceptance of each carriage after completion of cleaning
33.	ARA kit sampling during the final delivery
34.	Site visit to the external restoration workshop, where the movable objects are to be cleaned
35.	Discussion of the conservation treatment of the exterior of the carriages, carried out by the SNCB + visit to the workshop
36.	Visit to the "Train World" museum, the new storage location of two of the six carriages
37.	Visit to an external depot of the SNCB: possible new storage location for four of the six carriages
38.	Shifting of two carriages to the external SNCB depot (workshop) for the renovation of the exterior of the carriages and asbestos treatment
39.	Follow-up of the treatment of the exterior of the carriages by the KIK-IRPA
40.	Shifting of the two carriages to the new "Train World" museum + connection of the same to the dehumidifiers
41.	Climate measurements and follow-up in Train World and in the two carriages by the external firm and the KIK-IRPA
42.	Preparation of the more comprehensive advisory report: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Discussion of the new storage locations • Analysis of the general damage factors • Requirements relating to the carriages collection • Disaster plan • Concrete recommendations
43.	Completion of the contract: "Mechanical removal of mould and removal of dust from six carriages"
44.	Discussion of the project and the advisory report with the SNCB, the KIK-IRPA and the external (service) provider: further follow-up, bottlenecks, problems and additional treatments required
45.	Bi-monthly follow-up by the KIK-IRPA of the trains, the depot, the climate, disasters,
46.	Proposal to the KIK-IRPA to take charge of the aftercare of the 6 historic carriages through follow-up, for at least 1 year: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Supervision of the maintenance of the carriages • Inspection of climate, fragile materials, insect monitoring, etc. • Training of the SNCB personnel to enable them to take on the care and maintenance of the carriages in the future as well

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Marjolijn Debulpaep & Kaat Sneider
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Academic biography

MARJOLIJN DEBULPAEP is working at the Royal Institute for Cultural Heritage (KIK-IRPA, Brussels, Belgium) since 2001. As a consultant in preventive conservation, she became responsible for the preventive conservation unit in 2007. Her experience and expertise are in the field of conservation and risk management of cultural heritage (complexes of movable heritage). MA in History of Art and Archaeology, Degree in Conservation-Restoration of Paintings and professional courses in Preventive conservation, like the 2007 "Reducing Risks to Cultural Heritage" ICCROM-course in Sibiu and several courses at the Institut national du Patrimoine in Paris. In 2013 she organized a workshop with Rob Waller on "Assessing and managing risks to your collection" at the KIK-IRPA and in 2015 she launched the "RE-ORG Belgium" pilot project.

KAAT SNEIDERS started working in 2013 at the Royal Institute for Cultural Heritage (KIK-IRPA), where she was assigned as project leader of the long-term Big Stuff project: Conservation of historical train interiors invaded by fluffy stuff. Kaat has a Master in Conservation of Paintings. Since 2005 she has worked in the field of active en preventive conservation where she gained experience in many projects and museums in Belgium and abroad.

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